

An Analysis of Students' Learning Outcome and Experiences in A Graduate Biostatistical Methods Course

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Abstract

This study explores how students' learning outcomes and experiences relate to the software package used, class modality, and select individual characteristics in a graduate-level service biostatistical methods course at the University of Florida. Drawing on data collected across six course offerings between 2023 and 2025, taught with different modalities and different software packages, we find that in-person students generally outperform their online peers on all assessments, especially on complex assignments; among online students, the easier software SPSS appears to enhance both outcomes and overall experiences, whereas the more challenging software SAS seems to motivate further enrollment in additional statistics courses. These results suggest that software complexity and course delivery format may interact in meaningful ways.

Key Words: biostatistics education, public health education, statistics education, analysis of learning outcomes, course design, teaching pedagogy, data-driven case study

1. Introduction

A Graduate-level biostatistical methods course is required for all graduate certificate, master's and doctoral programs in the College of Public and Health Professions (PHHP) and the College of Medicine (COM) at the University of Florida. Students in this course come from a wide variety of programs and bring markedly different academic backgrounds and skill sets, which makes it challenging to teach effectively and meet their diverse needs. This study uses firsthand data to examine how a set of input variables relates to students' learning outcomes and learning experiences in the course.

1.1 About the Course

This comprehensive biostatistical methods course comprises four modules: Explanatory Data Analysis Methods, Producing Data, Probability, and Inferential Statistics. Topics range from single-variable explanatory data analysis methods, to both parametric and nonparametric inferential methods for examining relationships between two variables of various types, with all data analysis conducted using statistical software.

As a service course aiming at providing hands-on data analysis using statistical software, this course is designed based on the belief of "learning by doing" philosophy. There are no formal exams; instead, assessment is based on 14 weekly quizzes (15%), 8 conceptional homework assignments (40%), 4 software assignments (15%), and a four-part course project: Parts 1 - 3 (15%) include dataset selection and description, as well as one and two variable explanatory and inferential analysis generated using software, while Part 4 (15%) is a comprehensive discussion of 24 questions based on the outputs submitted for Steps 2 and 3.

To support such a diverse student population without sacrificing the quality or lowering learning objectives, we offer the course in four versions based on the statistical software used and course delivery format: (SAS¹, in person), (SAS, online), (SPSS², in person), and (SPSS, online). All

classes use the same course material developed from “*Biostatistics: A Foundation for Analysis in the Health Sciences*”³ and “*Statistics: The Art and Science of Learning from Data*”⁴, assignments, and assessment criteria.

1.2 Initial Motivation

As described above, this course is required for all graduate programs in the College of PHHP and College of Medicine at UF and has no prerequisites. Students in the course vary widely across multiple dimensions, including academic program enrolled, level of mathematics preparation, and prior exposure to statistics and statistics software. In addition, the student population spans a wide age range, from relatively young students (typical new college graduates) to experienced practitioners and even retired medical doctors who have been away from academia for decades.

The combination of highly diverse backgrounds and relatively large class sizes makes it challenging to meet all students’ needs. The primary motivation for this study is twofold: to evaluate the course based on student performance and feedback, and to inform potential program and course reforms.

1.3 Research Questions

This study investigates how the course delivery format, the software choice, and a set of student demographic and academic characteristics influence student learning. Research questions guiding this study include:

- (a) How does the course delivery format affect students’ learning outcome, experiences, and attitudes toward future statistics coursework?
- (b) How does the choice of statistical software affect student’s learning outcome, experiences, and attitudes toward future statistics coursework?
- (c) Which demographic or academic background characteristics, such as academic program enrolled, mathematical preparation, number of prior statistics courses, and prior exposure to statistical software, are significantly associated with students’ learning outcomes, experiences, and attitudes toward future statistics coursework, and in what ways?
- (d) How do demographic factors, the course delivery format, and the software choice interact to influence students learning?
- (e) What is the impact of this course regarding students’ attitude toward statistics?

2. Data Collection

2.1 Data Resources

Data used in this study were collected from six course offerings taught by the same instructor between 2023 and 2025, ensuring consistency and minimizing instructor-related and time-dependent variability. The dataset included 259 students who completed the courses, including 61 students in two online classes using SPSS in Spring 2024 and Spring 2025, 107 students in two online PHC 6052 classes in Fall 2023 and Fall 2024, and 91 students in two campus PHC 6052 classes in Fall 2024 and Fall 2024, respectively. Students in PHC 6050 used SPSS to perform all data analysis, while in PHC 6052 students used SAS to perform all data analysis.

The entire data file was combined from 5 different sources, including registration information, pre-semester survey, final project responses, post-semester survey, and Canvas gradebook records. Approximately 70% of the students are in master programs, 24% in doctoral programs, and the remainder in certificate, residency or non-degree programs. About 10% students have already completed calculus III and/or a linear algebra course, whereas over 30% have never taken calculus I. Similarly, more than 20% of students had experience with at least one programming language, while nearly 55% have never used any statistical software.

2.2 Variables Used

A total of 20 variables were included in this study, grouped into 10 input variables and 10 output variables. Detailed descriptions of these variables are provided in Appendix 1.

Input variables include 6 categorical variables, such as delivery format, software used, program enrolled, highest mathematical level, and pre-intention of taking additional statistics, and 4 numerical variables, including score of computing questions at the start of the course, number of undergraduate and graduate level statistics courses taken, and familiarity with course content at the beginning of the course (retrospectively self-reported at the conclusion of the course). Among these, course delivery format and software used are controllable, while the remaining eight are represent uncontrollable student demographic characteristics.

Output variables comprise 4 categorical and 6 numerical variables. Academic performance measures, including scores on assignments, quizzes, projects, final scores, and final letter grades, are used to assess learning outcomes. Learning experiences are evaluated based on perceived difficulty and fulfillment of learning objectives, while changes in students' intention to take additional statistics courses from the beginning to the end of the course are used to assess the course's impact on students' attitudes toward further formal statistical training.

3. Results

Statistical analyses were conducted on various combinations of input and output variables, and the results are presented based on course delivery format and software choice. All analysis were done using R (4.3.3)⁵.

3.1 Results for SAS Users: Online versus In-Person Students

To evaluate the impact of course delivery format, we focused on the four classes that used SAS for data analysis in the datafile. Two of these classes were conducted online, with a total of 107 students, while the other two were in- person classes, comprising a total of 91 students. Below, we compare both the input and output variables for these two groups.

3.1.1 Inputs

a). Academic Programs and Pre-Course Intention to Take Additional Statistics

Side-by-side comparisons of the distributions of academic programs and students' self-reported intentions to take further statistics courses for these two groups are presented below:

Figure1. Programs & Pre-Course Intention to Take Additional Statistics Courses: Online vs In-Person SAS Users

The p-values of the tests for these two variables were 0.0004 and 0.002, respectively, indicating that both the distribution of programs enrolled and the distribution of pre-courses intentions to take additional statistics courses differed significantly between online and in-person classes using SAS. This suggests that these two groups differed substantially in terms of program enrollment and attitudes toward further statistics coursework.

b) Mathematics, Statistics, and Software Preparation

Figure 2 presents side-by-side comparisons of the following input variables: the number of undergraduate (USTAT, top left panel), number of graduate statistics courses completed (GSTAT, top right panel), percentage of familiarity with course topics at the beginning of the semester (PF, middle left panel), self-reported retrospectively at the end of the course), score on basic computational questions from the pre-semester survey (CS Score, middle right panel), highest mathematical level attained (bottom left panel), and prior software experience (bottom right panel).

Figure 2. Mathematics, Statistics, and Software Preparation: Online vs In Person SAS Users

The p-values for the corresponding tests for these six variables across these two groups (from left to right, top to bottom) were 0.007, 0.303, 0.032, 0.967, 0.019, and 0.001, respectively. These results indicate that while the mean of number of graduate-level statistics courses taken and the mean basic computational score did not differ significantly, the mean number of undergraduate statistics courses taken, retrospective self-reported familiarity with course topics at the beginning of the semester, highest mathematical level, and prior software experience were significantly different for these two groups. On average, students in the in-person classes had completed more undergraduate statistics courses, reported higher familiarity with course content before the course, demonstrated stronger mathematical preparation, and had more prior software experience.

3.1.2 Outputs

a). Learning Outcomes

Figure 3 presents side-by-side comparisons of students' academic performance between these two groups, including scores on software assignments, conceptual assignments, software projects, weekly quizzes, and the final course score.

Figure 3. Course Performance: Online vs. In-Person SAS Users

The p-values of the tests (corresponding to panels from left to right, top to bottom) were 0.199, 0.032, 0.004, 0.033, 0.088, and 0.005. These results indicate that while students' performances on less complex assignments allowing multiple attempts, such as the software assignments and weekly quizzes, were comparable (in person students still outperformed their online students, but the differences were not statistically significant), in-person students performed significantly better on more complex, more time-intensive, and predominantly single-attempt assessments, including conceptual assignments, interpretation projects, software projects, and their final score. Additionally, the distribution of final letter grades did not differ significantly between two groups ($p = 0.362$), even though the mean final scores were significantly different (94.9 vs. 92.7, $p = 0.005$).

b). Learning Experiences

Figure 4 presents side-by-side comparisons of self-reported fulfillment of learning objectives and perceived course difficulty at the conclusion of the course for these two groups.

Although a larger portion of in-person students reported that their objectives were "fully met" (80.2% vs. 66.7%), this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.056$). In contrast, perceived difficulty levels differed markedly: while 50% of in-person students rated the course as "very easy" or "somewhat easy", only 31.7% of online students rated it so. This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.0004$).

However, given substantial demographic differences between these two groups, these outcomes cannot be attributed solely to course delivery format.

Figure 4. Learning Experiences: Online vs. In-Person SAS Users

3.2 Results of Online Classes: SPSS Users vs SAS Users

To evaluate the impact of software choice, we compared the four online classes: two classes that used SPSS with a total of 59 students the other two that used SAS with a total of 107 students for data analysis. As before, both input and output variables were examined for these two groups of students.

3.2.1 Inputs

a). Academic Programs and Pre-Course Intention to Take Additional Statistics

Figure 5 presents side-by-side comparisons of program enrollment and pre-course intention to take additional statistics courses at the beginning of the semester.

Figure 5. Programs & Pre-Course Intention to Take Additional Statistics Courses: Online SPSS Users vs. Online SAS Users

The p-values for the corresponding tests were < 0.0001 for the program enrollment, and 0.857 for pre-intention to take additional statistics courses. These results indicate the two groups differed significantly in program enrollment, whereas their initial intention to take additional statistics courses did not differ significantly.

b). Mathematics, Statistics, and Software Preparation

Figure 6 presents side-by-side comparisons of the following input variables: number of undergraduate (USTAT, top left panel) and the number of graduate statistics course (GSTAT, top right panel), percentage of familiarity of the course topics at the beginning of the semester retrospectively reported at the end of the course (PF, middle left panel), score on basic computational questions in pre-semester survey (CS Score, middle right panel), highest mathematical level (bottom left panel) and software experience (bottom right panel).

Figure 6. Mathematics, Statistics & Software Preparation: Online SAS Users vs. SPSS Users

The p-values for the corresponding tests (from left to right, top to bottom) were 0.722, 0.035, 0.422, 0.265, 0.715, and 0.123. These results indicate that SPSS and SAS users in the online classes were largely comparable regarding their mathematics, statistics, and software preparation. The only significant difference was the mean number of graduate-level statistics courses previously taken, with online SAS users, on average, have taken more such courses.

3.2.2 Outputs

a). Learning Outcomes

Figure 7 presents side-by-side comparisons of students’ academic performance, including scores on the software assignments, conceptual assignments, software projects, weekly quizzes, and final score between the two groups.

Overall, SPSS user had higher mean score on most assessment items (except Software Assignments). However, none of these differences were statistically significant. The p-value of the corresponding tests (from left to right, top to bottom) were 0.728, 0.482, 0.056, 0.419, 0.322, 0.264, and 0.315. It is worth noticing that the mean SP (score of software project) of SPSS users was over 3 points higher than SAS users, which may be considered practically meaningful, though not statistically significant ($p = 0.056$).

Figure 7. Learning Outcomes: SPSS Users vs SAS Users in the Online Classes

b). Learning Experiences

Figure 8 presents side-by-side comparisons of self-reported learning objectives fulfillment and perceived difficulty of the course at the conclusion of the course between the two groups.

Figure 8. Learning Experiences: Online SPSS Users vs Online SAS Users

The p-values for the corresponding tests were 0.032 for self-reported learning objective fulfillment and 0.398 for perceived difficulty at the end of the semester. These results indicate that perceived difficulty did not differ significantly between the two groups, whereas self-reported fulfillment of learning objectives did. Specifically, 85% of the SPSS users reported their learning objectives were “fully met” and 15% reported “partially met”, with no report of “not met”, In contrast, among line SAS users, approximately 67% reported “fully met”, 33% “partially met”, and 2.9% “not met”. Thus, even though the two groups were comparable in terms of learning outcomes and perceived

difficulty, their sense of objective fulfillment differed significantly: a notable larger proportion of online SAS users felt their learning objectives were not fully met.

4. Discussion

4.1 Impact of the Course

To assess the course’s impact on students’ attitude to further statistics training, we compared their intentions to take additional statistics at the beginning and at the end of the semester across three groups: SAS users in online classes, SAS users in in-person classes, and SPSS users in online classes. The side-by-side bar charts below in Figure 9 display how the distributions of their intentions changed over time for each group.

Figure 9. Intention to Take Additional Statistics Courses: Pre vs. Post

From the bar charts, it is evident that in both the in-person and online classes using SAS, a large proportion of students shifted from “Maybe” and “No” to “Yes” in their intention to take further statistics courses by the end of the semester. In the online classes using SPSS, many students moved from “No” to “Maybe,” and the proportion of “Yes” responses increased slightly.

For each group, the p-value of the corresponding test was < 0.001 , indicating that the distributions of self-reported intentions at the beginning and end of the semester differed significantly. Overall, more students became willing or open to taking additional statistics courses, providing strong evidence that the course positively influenced students’ attitudes toward statistics training.

4.2 Online SPSS vs In-Person SAS Users

We further compared the online classes using SPSS with the in-person classes using SAS. These two groups of students differed significantly in their program enrollment and in the average number of undergraduate and graduate statistics courses previously taken. However, their mathematics level, basic computation scores, and software experience at the start of the semester did not differ significantly.

Interestingly, all measured learning outcomes were comparable for these two groups. Although their self-reported intention to take further statistics courses, both at the beginning and at the end of the semester, differed significantly, their self-reported fulfillment of learning objectives ($p =$

0.634) and perceived course difficulty ($p = 0.129$) were not significantly different. This suggests that students can have comparable learning experiences regardless of their future interest in taking additional statistics courses.

Moreover, the findings suggest that when students have similar prior mathematics backgrounds and software experiences (regardless of other factors), using a simpler, more beginner-friendly software in an online course can help yield learning outcomes and experiences comparable to those of on-campus students using more complex software.

5. Conclusion

This study examines how software choice and course delivery format impact students' learning outcomes and learning experiences with various academic and demographic background in our first graduate-level biostatistical methods service courses.

For online classes, using less complex software tended to improve student performance and learning experiences, although the effect was not always statistically significant. Interestingly, exposure to more challenging software appeared to motivate some students to pursue additional coursework in statistics.

Among SAS users, in-person students consistently outperformed their online peers across all assessments, particularly on complex, time-intensive assignment, while reporting lower stress and stronger interest in further statistical training.

Overall, software complexity and delivery format interact in meaningful ways. Aligning them thoughtfully, for example, pairing more complex software with in-person instruction and selecting simpler tools for online classes, incorporating key elements of in-person instruction into online courses may help narrow performance gap, enhance both student success and the overall learning experience. At the same time, students' academic and demographic background remain important factors, warranting further investigation in future studies.

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Appendix: Variables Used

	Input	Output
Categorical	1. Delivery format (online or in person)	1. Objective fulfillment
	2. Software used for the class (SPSS or SAS)	2. Difficulty level perceived
	3. Program Enrolled	3. Post-intention of taking additional statistics courses
	4. Prior Software Experience	4. Final letter grade
	5. Math level	
	6. Pre-intention of taking additional statistics	
Numerical	1. Score of computing questions	1. Score on software assignments
	2. Number of undergraduate level statistics courses taken	2. Score on other assignments
	3. Number of graduate level statistics courses taken	3. Score on software project
	4. Familiarity with the contents (Retrospective)	4. Score on interpretation project
		5. Score on weekly quizzes
		6. Final score